

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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TASTE OF PLACE: HOW LOCAL-INGREDIENT SOURCING AFFECTS GUEST SATISFACTION AND MENU PROFITABILITY IN HOTEL RESTAURANTS

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Abstract. The study examines whether local ingredients on hotel menus make guests happier and more willing to pay. The topic is important because food and beverage services are no longer only a basic hotel function. They also influence guest experience, hotel image, destination identity, and possible menu value. The research uses a qualitative design based on semi-structured interviews with seven hotel guests. The interview data were analysed through manual thematic analysis. The findings indicate that local ingredients had a positive effect on guest satisfaction because respondents associated them with freshness, authenticity, better quality, and a stronger connection to the destination. However, willingness to pay was more conditional. Guests were open to a small premium only when the local claim was specific, believable, and supported by strong overall dining quality. The study concludes that local ingredients can strengthen guest satisfaction and moderate price acceptance, but they cannot replace the basic elements of restaurant quality such as taste, service, atmosphere, and value for money.

Keywords: Guest satisfaction, menu profitability, willingness to pay

Annotatsiya. Tadqiqot mehmonxona menyusidagi mahalliy ingredientlar mehmonlarni xursand qilish va to'lashga tayyorligini o'rganadi. Mavzu muhim, chunki oziq-ovqat va ichimliklar xizmatlari endi faqat asosiy mehmonxona vazifasi emas. Ular, shuningdek, mehmonlar tajribasi, mehmonxona imiji, maqsad identifikatori va mumkin bo'lgan menyu qiymatiga ta'sir qiladi. Tadqiqotda ettita mehmonxona mehmoni bilan yarim tizimli suhbatlar asosida sifatli dizayn qo'llaniladi. Intervyu ma'lumotlari qo'lda tematik tahlil orqali tahlil qilindi. Topilmalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, mahalliy ingredientlar mehmonlarning qoniqishiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatdi, chunki respondentlar ularni yangilik, haqiqiylik, yanada sifatli va belgilangan joyga kuchliroq aloqa bilan bog'lashdi. Biroq, to'lashga tayyorlik ko'proq shartli edi. Mehmonlar faqat mahalliy da'vo o'ziga xos, ishonchli va kuchli umumiy ovqatlanish sifati bilan qo'llab-quvvatlangan, kichik mukofotga ochiq edi. Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatadiki, mahalliy ingredientlar mehmonlarning qoniqishini va o'rtacha narxni qabul qilishni kuchaytirishi mumkin, ammo ular ta'm, xizmat, atmosfera va pul qiymati kabi restoran sifatining asosiy elementlarini almashtira olmaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: Mehmonlarning qoniqishi, menyuning rentabelligi, to'lashga tayyorlik

Аннотация. В исследовании рассматривается вопрос о том, делают ли местные ингредиенты в меню отелей гостей более довольными и готовыми платить больше. Эта тема важна, поскольку услуги питания и напитков перестали быть просто базовой функцией отеля. Они также влияют на впечатления гостей, имидж отеля, идентичность места назначения и возможную ценность меню. В исследовании использован качественный подход, основанный на полуструктурированных интервью с семью гостями отеля. Данные интервью были проанализированы с помощью ручного тематического анализа. Результаты показывают, что местные ингредиенты оказывают положительное влияние на удовлетворенность гостей, поскольку респонденты связывают их со свежестью, подлинностью, лучшим

качеством и более сильной связью с местом назначения. Однако готовность платить оказалась более условной. Гости были готовы к небольшой доплате только тогда, когда утверждение о местном происхождении было конкретным, убедительным и подкреплялось высоким общим качеством блюд. Исследование приходит к выводу, что местные ингредиенты могут повысить удовлетворенность гостей и снизить приемлемость цены, но они не могут заменить основные элементы качества ресторана, такие как вкус, обслуживание, атмосфера и соотношение цены и качества.

Ключевые слова: удовлетворенность гостей, рентабельность меню, готовность платить

INTRODUCTION

Hotel restaurants have become an important part of the total hospitality experience. Guests do not judge a hotel only through rooms and service. They also evaluate food, atmosphere, menu identity, and the feeling that the hotel reflects the destination. In this context, the idea of “taste of place” is important because food can help visitors experience the culture and identity of a location. The World Food Travel Association (2020) describes food tourism as travelling for a taste of place in order to get a sense of place. This idea is closely connected with local ingredients, because such ingredients can make the hotel dining experience feel less standard and more connected to the surrounding area.

The use of local ingredients is also linked to sustainability and local food systems. Local food is often connected with shorter supply chains, support for producers, seasonality, and more responsible consumption. However, research also warns that the effects of local food are not automatically positive in every situation. Enthoven and Van den Broeck (2021) explain that outcomes depend on product type, supply chain form, and country context. For hotel restaurants, this means that local sourcing can create value, but it can also bring challenges such as higher costs, seasonal availability, and the need for clear communication.

Previous studies show that some customers are willing to pay a premium for local food when the added value is clear (Alfnes & Sharma, 2010). Other hospitality studies show that sustainable restaurant practices can increase customer attitudes, satisfaction, and behavioural intentions when they are visible and credible (Ali & Khalil, 2023; Park et al., 2020). Nevertheless, there is still limited qualitative understanding of how hotel guests themselves interpret local ingredients on hotel restaurant menus. This creates the research problem of the present study.

Research Objective and Research Question

The central objective of the study is to analyse how local ingredients on hotel restaurant menus influence hotel guests' satisfaction and willingness to pay. The secondary objectives are to explore guests' awareness and perceptions of local ingredients, investigate how local ingredients affect dining satisfaction, examine how they shape reported willingness to pay, and develop practical suggestions for hotel managers on communication and value presentation. The main research question is: Do local ingredients on the hotel menu increase guest satisfaction and willingness to pay?

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review is based on several connected concepts: authenticity, perceived value, satisfaction, willingness to pay, sustainability, and menu profitability. These concepts explain why local ingredients may matter to hotel guests and why their effect is not always simple.

First, local food is strongly connected with authenticity and destination identity. Sims (2009) argues that local food can support a more sustainable tourism experience because it helps visitors feel closer to the place they are visiting. Björk and Kauppinen-Räsänen (2016) also show that local food can function as a destination attraction. In hotel restaurants, this is relevant because hotels can otherwise feel standardised and detached from the local environment. Local ingredients may help the restaurant become part of the destination experience rather than just a convenient food outlet.

Second, authenticity can influence satisfaction through quality perceptions. Zhang et al. (2019) show that authenticity is linked with food quality, service quality, physical environment, tourist satisfaction, and loyalty. This is useful for the present study because it suggests that authenticity is not only a symbolic idea. It can shape practical guest judgments about whether a meal feels good, believable, and worth remembering.

Third, perceived value helps explain why guests may respond to local ingredients. Zeithaml (1988) defines value as the customer's judgment of what is received compared with what is given up. In a hotel restaurant, guests do not judge value only by the food. They also judge price, service, atmosphere, menu explanation, and trust. Choe and Kim (2018, 2019) show that tourist local food value includes several dimensions, such as taste, quality, health, price, prestige, interaction, and learning value. This means local ingredients may create functional value through freshness, emotional value through pleasure, and symbolic value through place identity.

Fourth, willingness to pay is related to value but is not the same as satisfaction. Guests may like local ingredients and still refuse a large price increase. Alfnes and Sharma (2010) found that restaurant customers may pay more for locally produced food when the value is clear. However, research on green hotels also shows that price premiums depend on trust, visible performance, and real service quality (Damigos, 2023; Yang et al., 2024). Therefore, willingness to pay should be understood as conditional.

Finally, the literature on restaurant profitability and menu engineering shows that positive guest response does not automatically prove financial success. Thompson (2010) explains that restaurant profitability depends on pricing, menu mix, cost control, labour, and demand patterns. Noone and Cachia (2020) also show that menu decisions must consider substitute items and pricing relationships. Therefore, local sourcing may support a premium image, but its final financial effect cannot be concluded without actual menu and cost data. This is why the present thesis focuses empirically on guest satisfaction and willingness to pay, while treating menu profitability as a practical implication rather than a directly measured outcome.

The main research gap is that many studies focus on local food in tourism or restaurants generally, while fewer focus specifically on hotel restaurants. There is also a methodological gap because many studies use surveys or experiments, while less is known about how hotel guests explain their own views in detail. This study addresses part of that gap through qualitative interviews with hotel guests.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study used a qualitative research design. A qualitative approach was suitable because the aim was to understand how guests think and feel about local ingredients, not to test a statistical relationship. The research took the form of an exploratory study based on semi-structured interviews with hotel guests. This design allowed the researcher to ask guiding questions while also giving respondents space to describe their experiences in their own words.

Purposive sampling was used. Participants were selected because they had recently stayed in a hotel and eaten at least one meal in the hotel restaurant, had seen or been exposed to local ingredients on the menu, and were willing to reflect on their experience. Seven participants were included in the final analysis. The sample was small, but it allowed for detailed qualitative interpretation, which is appropriate for a bachelor-level interview study.

The interviews were conducted individually in a conversational format. They were audio-recorded with participant consent and then transcribed in written form. The questions covered the meaning of local ingredients, menu visibility, influence on food choice, satisfaction, freshness, authenticity, willingness to pay, price fairness, trust, staff explanation, and overall guest expectations.

The data were analysed using thematic analysis based on Braun and Clarke (2006). Coding was completed manually. The researcher read the transcripts several times, created initial codes such as “noticing local labels,” “freshness and quality,” “price fairness,” “trust in menu wording,” and “local as added value,” and then grouped these codes into broader themes. This process helped identify the main patterns across the interviews.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Table 1. Respondent profile

Respondent	Age	Gender	Education	Occupation
R1	24	Female	Bachelor's	Marketing assistant
R2	27	Female	Bachelor's	IT specialist
R3	29	Female	Master's	School teacher
R4	31	Female	Bachelor's	Bank officer
R6	35	Female	Master's	University lecturer
R8	31	Male	Bachelor's	Entrepreneur
R10	30	Male	Bachelor's	Business consultant

The results show that local ingredients had a clear positive effect on guest satisfaction, while their effect on willingness to pay was more careful and conditional. All seven respondents noticed local ingredients because the menu described them clearly. This means that local sourcing created value only when it was visible to the guest. Respondents stated that they would probably not notice ingredient origin if it was not communicated through the menu or staff explanation.

The first main theme was freshness, authenticity, and connection to place. Respondents connected local ingredients with fresher products, stronger quality expectations, and a meal that felt more linked to the destination. R3 stated that local vegetables or local cheese made the food feel “fresher and less industrial.” R6 explained that local ingredients made the meal feel more connected to the city. R8 added that travelling is about experience, not only sleeping in a hotel, so local ingredients made the restaurant more interesting. These statements support the idea that local ingredients created both sensory value and symbolic value.

The second theme was modest and conditional willingness to pay. All seven respondents said they could accept paying more, but only within a reasonable limit. No respondent supported a large or automatic premium. R1 said she would pay more only if the difference was not too big. R2 explained that price mattered more than the label. R10 noted that hotels already apply premium pricing, so the use of “local” ingredients should be supported by clear value for guests. This shows that local ingredients improve price acceptance only when guests understand the added value and believe the price is fair.

The third theme was the need for clear communication and trust. Respondents repeatedly said that general wording such as “local ingredients” was too vague. They preferred specific information about which ingredient was local, where it came from, or why it mattered in the dish. R4 said that if the menu only says “local ingredients,” she wants to know what is local. R6 said that a short story makes the claim feel real rather than only marketing. This finding is important because it shows that communication is part of value creation.

The fourth theme was that local ingredients are an enhancer, not a substitute for core restaurant quality. Respondents valued local sourcing, but they still placed taste, service, atmosphere, and value for money first. R1 called local ingredients an enhancer that strengthens a good experience but does not replace the basics. R10 described them as an added value, not the main value. This means local sourcing can improve an already good dining experience, but it cannot replace consistent food quality and professional service.

Table 2. Summary of key findings

Main finding	Evidence from interviews	Meaning for the thesis
Menu visibility matters	7 of 7 noticed local ingredients because the menu described them clearly	Local sourcing must be communicated before it can affect guest response
Satisfaction improves	7 of 7 said local ingredients improved dining satisfaction	Local ingredients create freshness, authenticity, and place connection
Willingness to pay is modest	7 of 7 accepted only a small or reasonable premium	Price acceptance depends on fairness, quality, and trust
Satisfaction is stronger than willingness to pay	6 of 7 clearly stated this pattern	Positive emotion appears more easily than extra spending
Local ingredients are not enough alone	7 of 7 said core quality remains essential	Taste, service, atmosphere, and value remain the foundation

The findings are consistent with the literature. They support Sims (2009), Björk and Kauppinen-Räsänen (2016), Kim et al. (2013), and Zhang et al. (2019), who show that local food can strengthen authenticity, destination image, satisfaction, and loyalty. The findings also support Alfnes and Sharma (2010) and Linnes et al. (2023), who suggest that consumers may accept a premium for local food. However, the present study adds nuance because it shows that hotel guests accept only modest premiums and only when quality and communication are strong. The results also support Park et al. (2020) and Ali and Khalil (2023), who argue that sustainable practices affect guest response most clearly when they are visible and understandable.

The discussion therefore shows that local ingredients can help answer the research question positively, but not automatically. They can increase guest satisfaction by adding freshness, authenticity, and a stronger connection to the destination. They can also make guests more willing to pay, but mainly when the price increase is moderate and clearly justified. The effect on satisfaction is stronger than the effect on willingness to pay.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The study concludes that local ingredients on hotel restaurant menus can improve guest satisfaction and support moderate willingness to pay. Respondents saw local ingredients as signs of freshness, care, authenticity, and place identity. Local ingredients made hotel dining feel less generic and more memorable. However, Guests did not view local ingredients as sufficient on their own. They remained highly attentive to

taste, service, atmosphere, price fairness, and menu credibility.

The main contribution of the study is its guest-centred explanation of local ingredients in hotel restaurants. It shows that local sourcing is not only a supply or marketing issue. It is also a meaning-making process. Guests first need to notice the local element, then decide whether it feels believable, and only then may it influence satisfaction or price acceptance. This process is important for hotel managers because it shows that buying local ingredients is not enough. The value must be translated into the guest experience.

Based on the findings, hotel restaurants should make local ingredients visible and specific on the menu. Instead of using only general phrases, menus should identify the local ingredient, mention the region, or briefly explain the origin. Staff should also be trained to explain local ingredients in a short, natural, and confident way. Pricing should remain moderate and clearly justified because guests are willing to accept only a reasonable premium. Finally, local sourcing should be used as part of a wider quality strategy that includes strong taste, good service, attractive atmosphere, and value for money.

The study has several limitations. The sample included only seven respondents, so the findings cannot be generalised to all hotel guests. The research used purposive sampling and focused only on guests with recent hotel restaurant experience. The data were self-reported, so they reflect stated views rather than actual purchasing behaviour. The study also did not include hotel managers, chefs, financial data, or menu profitability calculations. Therefore, the thesis can discuss perceived willingness to pay, but it cannot make direct claims about actual profit.

Future research could include a larger and more diverse sample, compare leisure and business travellers more systematically, and use mixed methods such as interviews combined with surveys or menu experiments. Future studies could also include hotel managers, chefs, and F&B directors in order to compare guest perceptions with operational decision-making. Finally, research using real menu sales data could examine whether guest willingness to pay is connected to actual menu performance and profitability.

REFERENCES

1. Ali, A. M. M., & Khalil, G. G. A. (2023). The influence of hotel restaurants' sustainable practices on customers' attitudes and behavioral intentions: Guest satisfaction as a mediator. *Journal of the Faculty of Tourism and Hotels – University of Sadat City*, 7(2/2), 59–88.
2. Alfnes, F., & Sharma, A. (2010). Locally produced food in restaurants: Are the customers willing to pay a premium and why? *International Journal of Revenue Management*, 4(3–4), 238–258.
3. Björk, P., & Kauppinen-Räsänen, H. (2016). Local food: A source for destination attraction. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 28(1), 177–194.
4. Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101.
5. Choe, J. Y. J., & Kim, S. S. (2018). Effects of tourists' local food consumption value on attitude, food destination image, and behavioral intention. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 71, 1–10.
6. Enthoven, L., & Van den Broeck, G. (2021). Local food systems: Reviewing two decades of research. *Agricultural Systems*, 193, Article 103226.
7. Kim, Y. G., Eves, A., & Scarles, C. (2013). Empirical verification of a conceptual model of local food consumption at a tourist destination. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 33, 484–489.
8. Linnes, C., Weinland, J. T., Ronzoni, G., Lema, J., & Agrusa, J. (2023). The local food supply, willingness to pay and the sustainability of an island destination. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, 6(3), 1328–1356.
8. Park, E. O., Chae, B. K., Kwon, J., & Kim, W. H. (2020). The effects of green restaurant attributes on customer satisfaction using the structural topic model on online customer reviews. *Sustainability*, 12(7), Article 2843.
9. Sims, R. (2009). Food, place and authenticity: Local food and the sustainable tourism experience. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 17(3), 321–336.
11. World Food Travel Association. (2020). *What is food tourism?* <https://www.worldfoodtravel.org/food-tourism>
12. Yang, J., Reza, M. N. H., Al Mamun, A., Masud, M. M., & Che Abdul Rahman, M. R. (2024). Predicting guest satisfaction and willingness to pay premium prices for green hotels. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 11, Article 1487.
13. Zhang, T., Chen, J., & Hu, B. (2019). Authenticity, quality, and loyalty: Local food and sustainable tourism experience. *Sustainability*, 11(12), Article 3437.

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